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EXPONENTIAL FEATURES IN THE FOURIER DOMAIN FOR PRISMA HYPERSPPECTRAL IMAGE SEGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

The advances in the field of remote sensing for Earth Observation allow many applications like precision agriculture, forest monitoring, to name a few. Hyperspectral imaging is the technique that offers a high spectral resolution offering such applications more information about the Earth surface, but the data volume to be stored and processed increases too. A reason for the increased data volume is the high intrinsic variability of spectral reflectance curves. In this paper we propose a feature extraction method for dimensionality reduction based on fitting a negative exponential function to the Fourier spectrum of each spectral reflectance curve. The hypothesis is that extracting an exponential profile of the Fourier amplitude spectrum, thus reducing the variability of the spectral signatures, will possibly impact the segmentation approach. We further implement a segmentation algorithm based on the extracted features and assess its performance.

Index Terms— remote sensing, hyperspectral image, exponential feature extraction, image segmentation

1. INTRODUCTION

Hyperspectral imaging is capable of capturing detailed spectral information about the Earth's surface with up to nano-meter spectral resolution. Both the increased spatial and spectral resolutions of nowadays satellites result in very large spectral data cubes. Each hyperspectral image pixel contains hundreds of spectral bands having different values function of the ground material and its properties. Due to the surface texture and the chemical content, as well as various polarization and scattering effects, there is a high variability of the pixel spectra, even for pure materials or end-members [5]. Consequently, there is a need for dimensionality reduction in many applications [15].

Various feature extraction techniques have been proposed in the literature, which emphasize certain image properties like pixel intensities, edges, color or texture information, image contrast [8]. Global features like the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) or HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients) are computed on the whole image, and local features like the widely-used LBP (Local Binary Pattern), SIFT or SURF [8] usually compare each pixel with its surrounding neighbor pixels. Morphological profiles represent multiscale feature extraction tools based on openings and closings by reconstruction with structuring elements of increasing size [14]; in the case of hyperspectral images, extended morphological profiles can be employed [4]. The purpose of all features extraction techniques is to compute invariants of the local patterns in the images.

Image segmentation represents the process of partitioning an image into multiple segments/objects [13]. Segmentation techniques can be divided into two broad classes: supervised and unsupervised, with unsupervised segmentation algorithms representing techniques that do not employ ground truth information [12]. A large number of unsupervised segmentation techniques have been proposed in the literature, from classical edge detection methods [3] and clustering techniques such as K-means [11] or mean shift [9], to more recent approaches such as the ones based on Fuzzy C-Means clustering (FCM) [2][7] or Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [1][3]. The advantage that unsupervised methods have over high-performance deep learning-based supervised approaches is that the latter category of techniques usually requires a large dataset for training, which can be unfeasible in some contexts [2].

In this paper we propose a feature extraction method for dimensionality reduction, which we further apply to pixel classification in order to perform image segmentation. The feature extraction is based on fitting a negative exponential function to the Fourier spectrum of the hyperspectral reflectance curve, for each pixel. The hypothesis is that using a fitted exponential rather than the raw data will reduce the variability of data and help the segmentation approach.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the proposed method, Section 3 the experimental results and Section 4 the conclusions and further work.

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2. PROPOSED METHOD

The negative exponential function is of generic shape $f(x)=ae^{bx}$ and the fitting process aims at determining the optimum values of the a and b parameters [16]. We chose the negative exponential due to the fact that the Fourier

Fig. 1. The pixel spectral reflectance curve.

Fig. 2. The Fourier spectrum (in blue) and the fitted negative exponential function ae^{bx} (in orange).

amplitude spectrum usually exhibits a very similar profile. The Fourier spectrum was computed using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) function on the pixel spectral reflectance curve $R(\lambda)$ and the fitting was performed using the fit function, both available in MATLAB.

Only half of the FFT values are used, due to the symmetry property of the Fourier spectrum. In addition, the phase information was disregarded. For classification we used the fuzzy c-means (FCM) clustering approach, also implemented in MATLAB [5]. In Fig. 1 we depict for one pixel the spectral reflectance curve and in Fig. 2 the Fourier amplitude spectrum together with the fitted negative exponential function which approximates it.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In what follows we present the experimental results we obtained for a PRISMA (“PRecursores IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa” or “Hyperspectral Precursor of the Application Mission”) hyperspectral image [10]. PRISMA images are acquired both in the VNIR and SWIR domains, with a spectral resolution of approx. 14 nm. We considered a Level 1 PRISMA product over the area to the North of Brasov City, Romania, with the latitude = 45.8784 and longitude = 25.5464 coordinates. For experiments, we used only the 66 spectral bands in the VNIR domain (400 nm – 1010 nm) to ensure continuity of the spectrum for the computation of FFT. The image was cropped in order to improve the running time of the MATLAB implementation of the proposed approach. Fig. 3-(a) is the color RGB composite image of the cropped scene. In

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order to represent the color RGB composite of the original hyperspectral image, we used the band-selection and the following three bands have been selected: 33, 49 and 57 (corresponding to approx. 674 nm, 542 nm and 446 nm) and mapped to the red, green and blue channels, respectively. Fig. 3-(b) and (c) represent the pseudo-images of the negative exponential

Fig. 3. Experimental results on a cropped area of a PRISMA hyperspectral image: (a) color RGB composite, (b) $\log(a)$ pseudo-image, (c) $\text{abs}(b)$ pseudo-image, (d) FCM in the $(\log(a),|b|)$ space, (e) FCM in the (a,b) space, (f) FCM on all 66 spectral bands.

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parameter values, $\log(a)$ and $\text{abs}(b)$ respectively. Fig. 3-(d) and (e) depict the resulting segmentation map based on pixel classification in the $(\log(a), |b|)$ and (a,b) feature space, respectively, using FCM for a number of clusters $N_c=4$. Each pixel was assigned to a class based on its highest membership value. Note that the resulting classes roughly correspond to the four main types of land cover present in the scene: water ponds, wild vegetation, and two types of agricultural crops (greenish and yellowish).

The assessment of the accuracy of the proposed segmentation algorithm was performed in three ways. The first one consisted of a comparison of the segmentation result with a manually generated ground truth (GT) image. This GT image is shown in Fig. 4-(a) and contains regions belonging to three different classes (water - represented in blue, yellowish agricultural crops – red and greenish ones – green). The GT image was produced by manually selecting some known areas.

The second assessment method is performed using the segmentation map provided by PRISMA. An example of this type of segmentation map is shown in Fig. 4-(b). The vertical lines represent error pixels and are ignored. The third method consisted of applying FCM clustering directly on the 66 spectral bands in their original domain; the segmentation result is shown in Fig. 3-(f). The segmentation accuracy was assessed using the following metrics: rand index or accuracy, Dice coefficient and border error (BE) [17] defined with (1),

$$BE = \text{area}((A \cup M) - \text{area}(A \cap M)) / \text{area}(M) \quad (1)$$

where A is the automatically-segmented area and M is the manual segmentation from the GT.

These values are presented in Table 1, where a_1 , a_2 and a_3 represent the water, yellowish and greenish crop classes. From the first two lines of Table 1, one notices that our method performs better for the water class (a_1) and the greenish crops (a_3). If we compare our method with a classic FCM applied on all 66 spectral bands (lines 1 and 3 from Table 1), one notices slightly smaller results for classes a_1 and a_3 , and better results for class a_2 .

Fig. 4. a) The GT image; b) PRISMA segmentation map provided by ASI along with the L1 product

Table 1 – segmentation performance evaluation.

Segm. type	BE a_1	RI a_1	Dice a_1	BE a_2	RI a_2	Dice a_2	BE a_3	RI a_3	Dice a_3
FCM	0.36	0.98	0.82	3.42	0.78	0.36	2.04	0.81	0.45
PRISMA	4.47	0.73	0.02	1.64	0.89	0.29	5.53	0.49	0.25
FCM66	0.34	0.98	0.83	4.63	0.71	0.29	1.80	0.83	0.46

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

In this paper we propose a feature extraction method for dimensionality reduction of a hyperspectral image data volume. The Fourier spectrum of the spectral reflectance curve of each image pixel is computed and then, its amplitude is approximated by fitting a negative exponential. Thus, for each hyperspectral image pixel only two values - the a and b parameters of the exponential function - are kept. We further applied fuzzy-c-means (FCM) clustering segmentation on the (a,b) parametrized image. The segmentation result was assessed in terms of accuracy, Dice coefficient and border error. Our method outperforms the segmentation included in the L1 product of the PRISMA image for two of the classes (water and greenish crops). We conclude that the proposed feature extraction slightly improves the segmentation, but further experiments are required.

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